

Nietzsche, Beethoven, and the Composition of History

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I've come to think of Friedrich Nietzsche's *Untimely Meditations*¹ as a sort of symphony, in which the philosopher-as-composer explores two distinct, but nevertheless related, themes of culture and character, *Kultur* and *Bildung*, via a series of four philosophical "movements," each represented by one of the four essays.² The first movement, if you will, *David Strauss as Writer and Confessor*, treats the themes from the perspective of theology and history of religion. The essay's first section presents a definition of *Kultur*³ that remains operative throughout all four of the *Untimely Meditations*:

Culture is a unity of artistic style that manifests itself throughout all the vital self-expressions of a people. However, vast knowledge and pedantic learning are neither a requisite means to, nor a symptom of, culture; indeed, these generally prove themselves most compatible with the opposite, with barbarism—that is, with absence of style, or the chaotic hodgepodge of all styles. (Nietzsche, 1995, p. 9)⁴

The second untimely meditation, or movement, in the *Kultur-Bildungs* symphony, *On the Advantages and Disadvantages of History for Life*, constitutes a set of variations on the advantages and disadvantages of monumental, antiquarian, and critical history. Here, too, Nietzsche explains:

The culture of a people ... is the antithesis of that barbarism once termed—and in my opinion, rightfully so—the unity of an artistic style that manifests itself throughout all the vital self-expressions of a people.... A people to whom we attribute a culture should in all reality be but a single, vital unity and not fall apart so miserably into inner and outer, content and form. (Nietzsche, 1995, p. 111)⁵

Nietzsche also addresses the theme in a passage from an unpublished essay titled "Philosophy in Hard Times" found in his notebooks from the spring of 1873, the same period during which he wrote the essay on history. "Redefinition of culture: a single temperament and key (*Stimmung*) composed of many originally hostile forces, which now enable a melody to be played" (Nietzsche, 1979a, p. 109).⁶ The third movement of the *Untimely Meditations* examines the *Kultur-Bildung* complex from the perspective of *Schopenhauer as Educator*, and the fourth suggests that the music-dramas of *Richard Wagner at Bayreuth* might lead to the rebirth of *Bildung* in contemporary German *Kultur*.

While a great deal of interpretive energy has been expended on the first half of Nietzsche's essay on history, most notably Hayden White's (1975) definition of historiographic tropes and Michel Foucault's (1980) reflections on the genealogy of origins, the second half of the essay, which frequently alludes to music, musical acoustics, and musical composition, has received far less attention. Concentrating on this second portion of the essay, I will argue that Nietzsche's

conception of history as musical variations composed on a well-known musical theme constitutes both a philosophy of history and a pedagogical method for teaching about the past.

The essay makes direct reference to types of historians via figurative comparisons to musicians. Beginning in section §6, the reader is introduced to the Historical Virtuoso, a personification of the least advantageous relation to history outlined in the essay's preceding pages. Soon after, the Composer of History, who represents a vital and creative relation to the past, takes the stage. And, in the essay's final section, we are invited into the Republic of Genius, where the musical perception of exceptionally resonant voices of the past, when apprehended in the present, become timeless.⁷

The Historical Virtuoso and the Composer of History

Nietzsche's Historical Virtuoso plays a lyre that resonates at the mere mention of "diverse ages and persons," thus "nothing human is alien" to his sensibilities. Accordingly, he is nothing more than a passive "sounding-board whose reflected tones act upon other similar sounding-boards until the whole of the air of the age is confused" by the competing echoes. "[I]t seems," Nietzsche continues, "that only the harmonics, as it were, of the original historical note remain audible" and, as a consequence, the "harshness and power of the original can no longer be divined in the thin and shrill sound of the lyre strings." The fundamental tone, which "usually awakened deeds, difficulties, and terrors," can no longer be discerned.⁸ "It is as if the *Eroica* symphony had been arranged for two flutes, and were intended for the benefit of dreaming opium smokers" (p. 124).⁹

Shortly after, Nietzsche objects to the work of a "celebrated historical virtuoso," likely such a "scientific" historian as Leopold Ranke or his ilk, who "no longer have anything to teach us" (p. 127).¹⁰ "To conceive of history objectively this way is the silent work of the dramatist" for whom "all things are interrelated." The great failing of the Historical Virtuoso is the appropriation of the past for present self-interest. Thus history is little more than a vehicle to demonstrate technical facility, just as the 19th century virtuoso appropriates extant musical works for professional and personal aggrandizement.¹¹ The virtuoso "weaves isolated events into a totality—always with the presupposition that a unity of plan must be inserted into the things if it is not already inherent in them" (p. 126)¹² and "force[s] the past to fit" the present's "fashionable triviality" (p. 125).¹³

The final reference to this metaphorical figure points directly to Hegel, who "ought to have said that everything that came after him was properly considered merely as a musical coda to the world historical rondo" (p. 143). In this passage, Nietzsche, the musician and would be composer, parodies the repetitive, three-part structure of Hegel's dialectic by comparing it to the rondo's large scale ternary organization, comprised of numerous subsidiary three-part structures. Beneath this remark, with its Nietzschean combination of the droll and the caustic, is a more sophisticated joke. In its most academic form, the rondo creates what can be heard as a dialectical alternation between the primary theme and the episodic material, i.e. ABACABA, yet inasmuch as a verbatim statement of the primary theme follows each episode, there is no musical *Aufhebung*.

While the Virtuoso composes history in rondo form, the true historian, the Composer of History, prefers the theme and variation form, in which the inspired re-working of a “well known (*ein bekanntes*) melody” leads to its elevation.

The true historian must have the power to reformulate a well-known, perhaps commonplace theme, an everyday melody, into a comprehensive symbol, and thereby intimating in the original theme a whole world of profundity, power, and beauty never before heard. (Nietzsche, 1995, p. 129)¹⁴

Like the Composer of History, the true historian (*der ächte Historiker*), reformulates “an age old truth (*Allbekannte*) into something never before heard” (p. 129).¹⁵ Through continued attention to a recurrent historical theme a “comprehensive symbol” can be created, one that is both untimely and advantageous to life. Put another way, rather than preserving history for egoistic reasons, the Composer of History finds the past a source of creativity in the present. The metaphor of the Composer of History becomes all the more compelling, and does even more philosophical work, if, as I believe, Nietzsche had in mind Beethoven's op. 120, the so-called Diabelli Variations (or *Veränderungen über einen Walzer*) for solo piano, as a model for such a composition.

Beethoven's Veränderungen

Nietzsche's description of the Composer of History is strikingly similar to the characterization of Beethoven found in Wagner's 1870 essay, titled simply "Beethoven," commemorating the 100th anniversary of the composer's birth. Nietzsche first read the essay, in manuscript form, in 1870. It was published in Wagner's *Sämtliche Schriften und Dichtungen*, Volume IX (1872), and the composer presented the first nine volumes of his collected works to the young philosopher in the fall of 1873, while Nietzsche was at work on the Second *Untimely Meditation*. In the essay Wagner contrasts Beethoven, "the Genius of Music," with his predecessors, mere "virtuosos" who "placed the candle of art-dexterity in front of [music] instead of at its back, to light it up" (p. 86). Likewise, Beethoven "emancipated melody ... from the influences of 'shifting taste' and raised [it] to an eternal purely-human type" (p. 103).

Nietzsche first encountered Beethoven's works for solo keyboard as an adolescent piano student. In 1865 he purchased A.B. Marx's *Ludwig van Beethoven: Leben und Schaffen* (1859). Beethoven's piano works were also on Nietzsche's mind, and under his fingers, late in 1872. In the draft of a letter to Hans von Bülow, dated 29 October 1872, Nietzsche (1969/1996) responds to the conductor's candid criticisms of his efforts as a composer: "I shall try then to take a musical cure; and perhaps I shall remain, if I study Beethoven sonatas in your edition, under your tutelage and guidance" (p. 107). In the 1871 critical edition of Beethoven's works for piano, von Bülow describes op. 120 as "the real microcosm, as it were, of Beethoven's genius, indeed even a portrayal of the essence of the whole world of musical composition" (Bülow & Lebert, 1871).¹⁶

Beethoven's op. 120 was the result of a project initiated by the musician Anton Diabelli (Figure 1) in 1819. The music publisher's aim was to solicit a collection of

Variations for the Pianoforte,
on a Given Theme,
Composed by the Most Excellent Composers and Virtuosi
in Vienna and the I. & R.
Austrian States

Figure One. Diabelli's Theme

Beethoven was among those invited to make a contribution, but instead he set the theme aside. When he returned to it some years later, the composer used the theme as the basis for an independent composition. Beethoven's 32 variations on Diabelli's theme were published independently as op. 120¹⁷ in 1823 (Figure 2) and as the first volume of a two-volume set in 1824.¹⁸

Figure Two. Cover page of op.120 (Vienna, Diabelli 1823).

While op. 120 is popularly known as the *Diabelli-Variationen*, and Diabelli titled it *Große Veränderungen über einen Walzer*, Beethoven’s preferred title for the work was *Große Veränderungen über einen bekannten ‘Deutschen’*. According to the Beethoven biographer Maynard Solomon (2003), at the beginning of the 19th century the designation *Deutsché* referred to "a familiar theme-type—a German dance or waltz, or *Ländler*—one that is redolent of the commonplace" (p. 17). The designation *Veränderungen*, or transformations, indicates the degree to which Beethoven considered his treatment of the pre-existing material to be more than decorative.¹⁹

In op.120 Beethoven presents an abbreviated history of music. In Variation 6 (Figure 3) he parodies the theme and variations treatment of popular melodies by such composer-performers as Kalkbrenner and Moscheles, examples of those self-serving compositions of the (world-historical) virtuoso Nietzsche finds so inartistic.²⁰ Inasmuch as Beethoven's early career was based, in part, on his reputation as a virtuoso pianist, with exceptional improvisational abilities, his parody of the virtuoso is also a self-parody of his own early identity.

Figure Three. var. 6.

Additionally, there are clear references to the Protestant chorale in Variation 20 and the learned counter-point of Bach in Variations 24 and 32. In Variation 31 (Figure 4) there is a quotation from Bach's *Goldberg-Variationen* (BWV 988).

Figure Four. var. 31.

Beethoven also refers to the rhythmic sequences of Handel's overtures and, in Variation 22 (Figure 5), he incorporates the aria *Nozze e giorno faticar* from Mozart's *Don Giovanni*.

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Allegro molto alla „Notte e giorno fatica“ di Mozart.

VAR. XXII.

The image shows the musical score for Variation XXII. It consists of three systems of music. The first system is a piano introduction with a treble clef and a bass clef. The second system continues the piano introduction. The third system is the main variation, starting with a treble clef and a bass clef. The score includes various dynamic markings such as *p*, *f*, *cresc.*, and *pp*. There are also some performance instructions like *al. f.* and *piu. f.*.

Figure Five. var. 22.

Finally, in Variation 33 (Figure 6) Beethoven quotes the final movement of his own final piano sonata, *Arietta: Adagio molto, semplice e cantabile* (op. 111).²¹

82 (68)

Tempo di Minuetto moderato (ma non tirarsi dietro)(aber nicht schleppend.)

VAR. XXXIII.

The image shows the musical score for Variation XXXIII. It consists of three systems of music. The first system is a piano introduction with a treble clef and a bass clef. The second system continues the piano introduction. The third system is the main variation, starting with a treble clef and a bass clef. The score includes various dynamic markings such as *p grazioso e dolce*, *cresc.*, *dim.*, and *ritenuce*.

Figure Six. var. 33.

Thus Beethoven's variations are both historicizing and autobiographical, a means by which he situates himself within the horizon of music history and his previous compositions.²²

Given its synthesis of creative expression and historical judgment, Beethoven's op. 120 exemplifies the genuine historian's power to recast the past into something never before heard, i.e. Beethoven transforms a *bekanntes 'Deutsché'* just as the Composer of History transforms a *bekanntes Thema*. Beethoven's composition can also be heard as a genealogical endeavor in which new musical values supplant older ones, including those that informed the composer's earlier works. Said another way, by presenting a theme that reflects both the stylistic development of western music and his own biography as composer and performer, Beethoven treats the Diabelli's theme perspectively.

Auditory Perception and Der ächte Historiker

The seminal research of Hermann von Helmholtz in acoustics and auditory perception is another source for Nietzsche's musical framing of history. The German polymath was the first to explain, in physiological terms, the effects of vibrations in the air on the *cilia* of the inner ear. In both "On the Physiological Causes of Harmony in Music" (1857) and *On the Sensations of Tone* (1862), Helmholtz compares the ear's *cilia* to the strings of a piano to illustrate how the sympathetic vibration of certain of the *cilia* with an external sound is similar to the sympathetic vibration sometimes heard from the piano when another instrument plays a pitch matching the tuning of one of its strings.²³ Moreover, he claims that the ability to recognize and appreciate the upper partials of a musical pitch develops over time.

Such recognition allows the discrimination of timbres, or qualities of tone, and depends upon hearing the pitch's upper partials. Helmholtz (1862) insists that these "are difficult to hear," especially in the case of the "the human voice," and that "many skillful observers have failed to discover them. In fact, a peculiar act of attention is requisite to hear them [the upper partials], and unless we know how to perform this act, the tones remain concealed" (p. 66-68). In other words, it is possible to cultivate our hearing; however, this cultivation, or attunement, requires the withdrawal of one's attention from those acoustic phenomena of lesser importance, e.g. the tone's volume, its articulation, etc. Recent theories of auditory perception call this withdrawal of attention "hearing out."²⁴

For Nietzsche, the cultivated temperament that resonates with or is sympathetic to one voice of the past but not another is exactly what the Historical Virtuoso lacks. As indicated above, he hears everything and everything he hears is of equal importance. Hence he is unable to engage in the intentional acts of forgetting, to *hear out* the noise of irrelevant historical data, necessary for a healthy relation to history. This patently illogical demand—to intentionally forget that which is already known—becomes a bit more comprehensible when Helmholtz's explanation of the cultivation of hearing is kept in mind. Intentional forgetfulness is analogous to the habitual withdrawal of auditory attention from less important aspects to attend to more significant sounds, the upper partials that determine the timbre, or distinctive quality of the voice or instrument. A cultivated temperament renders one insensitive to one voice and sympathetic to another. If one cultivates the right sort of historical awareness, an activity requiring both knowledge of the past and understanding of one's self in the present, admittance to the Republic of Genius (Nietzsche, 1995, p. 151) awaits. There, voices with a noble *Stimmung*, ones with an elevated "temperament," "disposition," or "tone" call from one pinnacle of history to another, yet only those with a similarly noble *Stimmung* can discern their significance.

The work of the untimely historian does not, so Nietzsche argues, "carry forward any process," but instead allows us to "live contemporaneously" with the past. Nietzsche situates such history, freed from temporal constraints, in a Republic of Genius, a metaphor borrowed from Schopenhauer, where "one giant calls out to another across desolate expanses of time" (Nietzsche, 1995, p. 151).²⁵ These giants recognize one another by the individual resonance of their voices. In a literal sense, citizens of the republic need both a strong voice, able to project across the many epochs of history, and a discriminating ear, capable of discerning the

characteristic timbre of similarly distinguished voices. Later in the same passage he describes the finely tuned temperament able to hear the noble resonances of history as follows:

[A]nyone who seeks to break this education must help the youth express itself, must help illuminate ... the path of their unconscious resistance against this education and transform it into an outspoken and loudly sonorous awareness (*einem laut redenden Bewusstsein*). (p. 160)²⁶

With the more or less inscrutable phrase *einem laut redenden Bewusstsein*, Nietzsche attributes an acoustic property, loudness, to human consciousness, that peculiar and most problematic aspect of human experience lamented in the essay's early paragraphs.

Conclusion

The general intent of Nietzsche's Untimely Meditation on *The Advantages and Disadvantages of History for Life* is to create a just relation to history, one both well-tempered and discerning, i.e. one displaying *Stimmung*. In such a relation one cares less about heroes and their actions than the possibility of heroes and heroism. True historians adopt an aesthetic disposition, or *Stimmung*, toward the topic and strive to create "within themselves an image [of history] to which the future should conform" (p. 130).²⁷

Latent within Nietzsche's untimely meditation on history is a critique of contemporary pedagogical practices within the discipline along with a philosophy of education *in nuce*. The "fundamental characteristic of the modern human being," according to Nietzsche, is a "remarkable antithesis between an interior that corresponds to no exterior and an exterior that corresponds to no interior" (p. 109).²⁸ Furthermore, "modern cultivation (*Bildung*) is nothing living precisely because it cannot be comprehended without this antithesis: that is no real cultivation (*Bildung*), but rather only a kind of knowledge about cultivation (*Bildung*)" (p. 110).²⁹ The composer of history, one with an artistic disposition, or *Stimmung*, can integrate the outer and inner, the form and the content, the *Kultur* in which he lives and the *Bildung* he possesses. He alone can serve as educator and guide. Likewise, students with the greatest potential for such formation, or *Bildung*, already display a resistance, albeit unconsciously, to contemporary *Kultur* and its methods of historical education. Young people with such a temperament, or *Stimmung*, "will have forgotten much of what they learned." Indeed, these "young people" of the future may chart the "course and progress" of history in such a way that they are "deliver[ed] from the malady of history." They have become, perhaps for the first time, "human beings, and ceased to be human aggregates." For Nietzsche, "that is quite an accomplishment! There is still hope" (p. 165-66).³⁰

References

- Bambach, C. (1990). History and ontology: A reading of Nietzsche's second "Untimely Meditation." *Philosophy Today*, 34 (1990): 259-72.
- Barthes, R. (1977). The grain of the voice. In *Image-Music-Text* (pp. 179-189). (S. Heath, Trans.). New York: Noonday Press.
- Beethoven, L. v. (1823). *Veränderungen über einen Walzer*, op.120. Vienna: Cappi & Diabelli.
- Breazeale, D. (2000). Nietzsche, critical history, and *Das Pathos der Richterum*. *Revue Internationale de Philosophie*, 211 (1), 57-76.
- Bülow, H. v. (Commentary). (1871). *Sonaten und andere Werke für das Pianoforte*. By L. v. Beethoven. (S. Lebert & I. Faisst, Ed.). Stuttgart: J.G. Cotta.
- Burckhardt, J. (1943). *Force and freedom*. (J. Hastings, Trans.). New York: Pantheon.
- Burckhardt, J. (1958). *On history and historians*. (H. Zohn, Trans.). New York: Harper.
- Burckhardt, J. (1998). *The Greeks and Greek civilization*. (S. Stern, Trans.). New York: St. Martin's Press.
- Crescenzi, L. (1994). Verzeichnis der von Nietzsche aus der Universitätsbibliothek in Basel entliehenen Bücher (1869-79). *Nietzsche-Studien*, 23, 388-442.
- Diabelli, A. (1824). *Vaterländischer Künstlerverein Veränderungen für das Piano Forte*. Vienna: Diabelli and Co.
- Foucault, M. (1980). Nietzsche, genealogy, and history. In *Language, counter-memory, practice* (pp. 76-100). (D. Bouchard, Trans.). Ithaca: Cornell University Press.
- Helmholtz, H. (1954). *On the sensations of tone*. (A. J. Ellis, Trans.). New York: Dover.
- Helmholtz, H. (1995). On the physiological causes of harmony in music. In *Science and culture: Popular and philosophical essays* (pp. 46-76). (D. Cahan, Trans.). Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Kinderman, W. (1987). *Beethoven's Diabelli variations*. Oxford: Clarendon Press.
- Marx, A. B. (1859). *Ludwig van Beethoven: Leben und Schaffen*. Berlin: Janke.
- Newman, W. S. (1977, March). A chronological checklist of collected editions of Beethoven's solo piano sonatas since his own day. *Notes*, 33, (3), 503-30.
- Nietzsche, F. (1969/1996). *Selected letters of Friedrich Nietzsche*. (C. Middleton, Trans.). Indianapolis: Hackett Publishing Company.
- Nietzsche, F. (1979a). Philosophy in hard times. In *Philosophy and truth*. (D. Breazeale, Trans.). Atlantic Highlands, NJ: Humanities Press.
- Nietzsche, F. (1979b). The struggle between science and wisdom. In *Philosophy and truth*. (D. Breazeale, Trans.). Atlantic Highlands, NJ: Humanities Press.

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- Nietzsche, F. (1980a). Jenseits von Gut und Böse [Beyond good and evil]. *Jenseits von Gut und Böse; Zur Genealogie der Moral*. Kritische Studienausgabe (Vol. 5) (pp. 9-243). (G. Colli and M. Montinari, Eds.). Berlin: de Gruyter.
- Nietzsche, F. (1980b). *Nachgelassene Fragmente 1869-1874 [Posthumous fragments 1869-1874]*. Kritische Studienausgabe (Vol. 7). (G. Colli and M. Montinari, Eds.). Berlin: de Gruyter.
- Nietzsche, F. (1980c). Unzeitgemäße Betrachtungen II; David Strauss der Bekenner und der Schriftsteller [Untimely meditations III: David Strauss the confessor and the writer]. *Die Geburt der Tragödie; Unzeitgemäße Betrachtungen I-IV; Nachgelassene Schriften 1870-1873*. Kritische Studienausgabe (Vol. 1) (pp. 157-242). (G. Colli and M. Montinari, Eds.). Berlin: de Gruyter.
- Nietzsche, F. (1980d). Unzeitgemäße Betrachtungen II: Vom Nutzen und Nachtheil der Historie für das Leben [Untimely meditations II: On the use and disadvantage of history for life]. *Die Geburt der Tragödie; Unzeitgemäße Betrachtungen I-IV; Nachgelassene Schriften 1870-1873*. Kritische Studienausgabe (Vol. 1) (pp. 243-334). (G. Colli and M. Montinari, Eds.). Berlin: de Gruyter.
- Nietzsche, F. (1995). *Unfashionable observations*. (R. T. Gray, Trans.). Stanford: Stanford University Press.
- Nietzsche, F. (2002). *Beyond good and evil*. (J. Norman, Trans.). Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Solomon, M. (2003). *Late Beethoven: Music, thought, imagination*. Berkeley: University of California Press.
- Wagner, R. (1995). Beethoven. In *Richard Wagner's prose works* (pp. 57-127). (W. A. Ellis, Trans.). Lincoln: University of Nebraska Press.
- Wagner, R. (1872). Beethoven. In *Sämtliche Schriften und Dichtungen*, Vol. IX (pp. 75-157). Leipzig: E.W. Fritzsch.
- White, H. (1975). *Metahistory*. Baltimore: Johns Hopkins University Press.

Notes

¹ Today the four essays are typically grouped in a single volume, however they were released separately by Nietzsche's publisher. Thus I will refer to the essays individually. All quotations are from Richard Gray's excellent translation, *Unfashionable Observations* (1995). Because the traditional translation of the collection's title is *Untimely Meditations*, this designation will be used in what follows.

² This is an expanded version of the second in a series of talks on Nietzsche and the philosophy of education. It was presented at the 2011 session of the Society for the Philosophical Study of Education to the American Philosophical Association's Central Division.

³ Nietzsche uses *Kultur* and *Cultur* interchangeably in the essay. For consistency I will use the former.

⁴ Kultur ist vor allem Einheit des künstlerischen Stiles in allen Lebensäusserungen eines Volkes. Vieles Wissen und Gelernthaben ist aber weder ein nothwendiges Mittel der Kultur, noch ein Zeichen derselben und verträgt sich nöthigenfalls auf das beste mit dem Gegensatze der Kultur, der Barbarei, das heisst: der Stillosigkeit oder dem chaotischen Durcheinander aller Stile. (Nietzsche, 1980c, p. 159)

⁵ Die Cultur eines Volkes als der Gegensatz jener Barbarei ist einmal, wie ich meine, mit einigem Rechte, als Einheit des künstlerischen Stiles in allen Lebensäusserungen eines Volkes bezeichnet worden; diese Bezeichnung darf nicht dahin missverstanden werden, als ob es sich um den Gegensatz von Barbarei und schönem Stile handele; das Volk, dem man eine Cultur zuspricht, soll nur in aller Wirklichkeit etwas lebendig Eines sein und nicht so elend in Inneres und Aeusseres, in Inhalt und Form auseinanderfallen. (Nietzsche 1980d, p. 274)

⁶ Umschreibung der Kultur—als einer Temperatur und Stimmung vieler, ursprünglich feindseliger Kräfte, die jetzt eine Melodie abspielen lassen. (*Gedanken zu der Betrachtungen: Die Philosophie in Bedrängniss* §48; Nietzsche, 1980b, p. 713)

⁷ Two of the most clear-headed readings of the Second *Untimely Meditation* are those of Daniel Breazeale (2000) and Charles R. Bambach (1990). For the former, Nietzsche fails to provide adequate standards according to which the *ächte Historiker* exercises his *Pathos der Richterum*. "[T]here is no guarantee at all that new values will in fact spring up on the barren ground that has been devastated by critical history. It is just as likely, indeed, it is far more likely, that the critical historian—*qua* philosophical genealogist or active nihilist—will prepare the way for something else altogether: not the endlessly self-overcoming *Übermensch*, but the infinitely self-satisfied man-as-animal, the *last man*" (Breazeale, 2000, p. 74-76). Breazeale does, however, find a less robust version of the *ächte Historiker* in the genealogist of *The Gay Science* who, by yoking the *Pathos der Richterum* to the *Pathos der Wahrheit*, is "more than a scientific historian or philosophical laborer." (Breazeale, 2000, p. 76). Rather, he traces "the genealogies of our

highest values, in the hope that new values will eventually arise to take the place made vacant by the critical (self-) destruction of the older ones" (Breazeale, 2000, p. 74). While Bambach is more sanguine about the *Pathos der Richterum*, he nevertheless asks, "If all past happenings are valued and re-valued according to the demands of the moment, then does history not merely become the mirror for Narcissus' ardent gaze" (Bambach, 1990, p. 266)? Bambach, like Breazeale, reads forward, as it were, and also finds a way around the impasse in *The Gay Science* where Nietzsche reformulates his critique of historicism. There Bambach finds a "historical ontology" able to address the "problems of language, interpretation, lived experience, and historical being" (p. 270).

⁸ Clearly, Nietzsche's attribution of musical qualities to culture bears some similarity to Schopenhauer's attribution of musical qualities to the will in his *World as Will and Representation*.

⁹ Nun stelle man sich den historischen Virtuosen der Gegenwart vor Augen: ist er der gerechteste Mann seiner Zeit? Es ist wahr, er hat in sich eine solche Zartheit und Erregbarkeit der Empfindung ausgebildet, dass ihm gar nichts Menschliches fern bleibt; die verschiedensten Zeiten und Personen klingen sofort auf seiner Lyra in verwandten Tönen nach: er ist zum nachtönenden Passivum geworden, das durch sein Ertönen wieder auf andere derartige Passiva wirkt: bis endlich die ganze Luft einer Zeit von solchen durcheinander schwirrenden zarten und verwandten Nachklängen erfüllt ist. Doch scheint es mir, dass man gleichsam nur die Obertöne jedes originalen geschichtlichen Haupttones vernimmt: das Derbe und Mächtige des Originals ist aus dem sphärisch—dünnen und spitzen Saitenklänge nicht mehr zu errathen. Dafür weckte der Originalton meistens Thaten, Nöthe, Schrecken, dieser lullt uns ein und macht uns zu weichlichen Genießern; es ist als ob man die heroische Symphonie für zwei Flöten eingerichtet und zum Gebrauch von träumenden Opiumrauchern bestimmt habe (Nietzsche, 1980d, p. 288).

¹⁰ Ueberhaupt fällt mir auf, dass solche Historiker, wie jener, von dem wir einen Satz anführten, nicht mehr belehren, sobald sie allgemein werden und dann das Gefühl ihrer Schwäche in Dunkelheiten zeigen (Nietzsche, 1980d, p. 291).

¹¹ The matter of virtuosity again surfaces in notes from 1875 for a projected work, titled *The Struggle Between Science and Wisdom*, in which Nietzsche objects to the dialectical virtuosity of Plato's Socrates. Here Nietzsche claims, echoing the line of argumentation developed in *The Birth of Tragedy*, that "Greek music and philosophy developed side by side" and continues with the observation, "So much depends upon the development of Greek culture, since our entire occidental world received its original impulse there from." However, "the more recent and decadent Hellenism has had the greatest historical power" thus "the older Hellenism was always falsely judged." "The danger for the Greeks lay in *virtuosity* in all genres. With Socrates the virtuosos of living begin. Socrates, the new dithyramb, the newer tragedy, *the invention of the rhetorician*. *The rhetorician is a Greek invention of later times!*" He concludes, "It is a splendid thing that the ancient philosophers were able to live so freely *without thereby turning themselves into fools and virtuosos*" (Nietzsche, 1979, p. 133-34). Likewise, Nietzsche speaks pejoratively of virtuosity in *Beyond Good and Evil*: "I specially mention Delacroix, the nearest related to Wagner; all of them great discoverers in the realm of the sublime, also of the loathsome and

dreadful, still greater discoverers in effect, in display, in the art of the show-shop; all of them talented far beyond their genius, out and out VIRTUOSI, with mysterious accesses to all that seduces, allures, constrains, and upsets; born enemies of logic and of the straight line..." (Nietzsche, 2002, p. 149). (Ich hebe Delacroix hervor, den Nächstverwandten Wagner's -, allesammt grosse Entdecker im Reiche des Erhabenen, auch des Hässlichen und Grässlichen, noch grössere Entdecker im Effekte, in der Schaustellung, in der Kunst der Schauläden, allesammt Talente weit über ihr Genie hinaus -, Virtuosen durch und durch, mit unheimlichen Zugängen zu Allem, was verführt, lockt, zwingt, umwirft, geborene Feinde der Logik und der geraden Linien... [Nietzsche, 1980a, p. 202-203]).

¹² In dieser Weise die Geschichte objectiv denken ist die stille Arbeit des Dramatikers; nämlich Alles aneinander denken, das Vereinzelte zum Ganzen weben: überall mit der Voraussetzung, dass eine Einheit des Planes in die Dinge gelegt werden müsse, wann sie nicht darinnen sei (Nietzsche, 1980d, p. 290).

¹³ ...ihre Arbeit ist, die Vergangenheit der zeitgemässen Trivialität anzupassen (Nietzsche, 1980d, p. 289).

¹⁴ Of course, rondo form is marked by repetitions of a single motive between which contrasting motives, or episodes, are interspersed. Throughout the 18th and 19th Centuries this lighthearted and often rollicking movement, that made fewer demands on listeners, was typically used as the conclusion of multi-movement, instrumental works.

¹⁵ The entire passage reads: *Nur aus der höchsten Kraft der Gegenwart dürft ihr das Vergangene deuten*: nur in der stärksten Anspannung eurer edelsten Eigenschaften werdet ihr errathen, was in dem Vergangnen wissensund bewahrenswürdig und gross ist. Gleiches durch Gleiches! Sonst zieht ihr das Vergangene zu euch nieder. Glaubt einer Geschichtschreibung nicht, wenn sie nicht aus dem Haupte der seltensten Geister herausspringt; immer aber werdet ihr merken, welcher Qualität ihr Geist ist, wenn sie genöthigt wird, etwas Allgemeines auszusprechen oder etwas Allbekanntes noch einmal zu sagen: der ächte Historiker muss die Kraft haben, das Allbekannte zum Niegehörten umzuprägen und das Allgemeine so einfach und tief zu verkünden, dass man die Einfachheit über der Tiefe und die Tiefe über der Einfachheit übersieht (Nietzsche, 1980d, p. 293-294).

¹⁶ [32] *Sonaten und [17] andere Werke für das Pianoforte*, unter Mitwirkung von Immanuel Faisst, bearbeitet und herausgegeben von Dr. Sigmund Lebert (und Dr. Hans von Bülow). Stuttgart: J.G. Cotta, 1871. According to William S. Newman's "Chronological Checklist of Collected Editions of Beethoven's Solo Piano Sonatas Since His Own Day" (1977), von Bülow supplied commentary for the last five sonatas, i.e. op. 101, 106, 109, 110, 111, and the *andere Werke*, including op. 120.

¹⁷ Diabelli included the following introductory note in the 1823 edition: "We present here to the world Variations of no ordinary type, but a great and important masterpiece worthy to be ranked with the imperishable creations of the old Classics—such a work as only Beethoven, the greatest living representative of true art—only Beethoven, and no other, can produce. The most original

structures and ideas, the boldest musical idioms and harmonies are here exhausted; every pianoforte effect based on a solid technique is employed, and this work is the more interesting from the fact that it is elicited from a theme which no one would otherwise have supposed capable of a working-out of that character in which our exalted Master stands alone among his contemporaries. The splendid Fugues, Nos. 24 and 32, will astonish all friends and connoisseurs of serious style, as will Nos. 2, 6, 16, 17, 23, &c. the brilliant pianists; indeed all these variations, through the novelty of their ideas, care in working-out, and beauty in the most artful of their transitions, will entitle the work to a place beside Sebastian Bach's famous masterpiece in the same form. We are proud to have given occasion for this composition, and have, moreover, taken all possible pains with regard to the printing to combine elegance with the utmost accuracy."

¹⁸ The second volume contained the 50 variations by the other "Most Excellent Composers and Virtuosi in Vienna and the I. & R. Austrian States" and was titled *Vaterländischer Künstlerverein*.

¹⁹ The type of treatment Beethoven gives Diabelli's theme is now categorized as 'amplifying variations,' but it seems likely that op.120 occasioned the term.

²⁰ In musicological parlance, the term parody is descriptive and more or less neutral; thus, strictly speaking, all of the variations in which Beethoven composes 'in the guise' of another musical style are parodies.

²¹ For a more complete discussion of Beethoven's op. 120, and references to the composer's op.111, see *Beethoven's Diabelli Variations* by William Kinderman (1987).

²² By 1820 Beethoven had composed over 60 theme and variation sets, either as separate works or as movements of larger works (Solomon, 2003, p. 302). Maynard Solomon (2003), Beethoven biographer with a pronounced psychoanalytic bent, says of the form, "[T]he theme is like the manifest dream—a simple, condensed sequence of images masking an infinity of latent dream thoughts. The manifest dream is deceptively simple, wrapped in disguises of distortion, censorship, condensation, and displacement. Analysis (variation) pierces these veils; recollection fills the dream (the theme) with a significance that illuminates the past and points toward future possibilities of transcendence and fulfillment" (p. 303).

²³ According to Luca Crescenzi (1994), records show Nietzsche borrowed Helmholtz's *Die Lehre von den Tonempfindungen* (1863) from the Basel library between 1870-73.

²⁴ It is because most modern hearing aids cannot hear-out ambient noise that they are unsatisfactory to many with hearing deficits.

²⁵ Dank der Geschichte, die ein solches Zusammenwirken zulässt, sie leben als die Genialen-Republik, von der einmal Schopenhauer erzählt; ein Riese ruft dem anderen durch die öden Zwischenräume der Zeiten zu... (Nietzsche, 1980d, p. 317).

²⁶ The entire passage reads: Immerhin: es giebt jetzt vielleicht hundert Menschen mehr als vor hundert Jahren, welche wissen, was Poesie ist; vielleicht giebt es hundert Jahre später wieder hundert Menschen mehr, die inzwischen auch gelernt haben, was Cultur ist, und dass die Deutschen bis jetzt keine Cultur haben, so sehr sie auch reden und stolziren mögen. Ihnen wird das so allgemeine Behagen der Deutschen an ihrer "Bildung" ebenso unglaublich und läppisch vorkommen als uns die einstmalig anerkannte Klassicität Gottscheds oder die Geltung Ramlers als eines deutschen Pindar. Sie werden vielleicht urtheilen, dass diese Bildung nur eine Art Wissen um die Bildung und dazu ein recht falsches und oberflächliches Wissen gewesen sei. Falsch und oberflächlich nämlich, weil man den Widerspruch von Leben und Wissen ertrug, weil man das Charakteristische an der Bildung wahrer Culturvölker gar nicht sah: dass die Cultur nur aus dem Leben hervorzunehmen und herausblühen kann; während sie bei den Deutschen wie eine papierne Blume aufgesteckt oder wie eine Ueberzuckerung übergegossen wird und deshalb immer lügnerisch und unfruchtbar bleiben muss. Die deutsche Jugenderziehung geht aber gerade von diesem falschen und unfruchtbaren Begriffe der Cultur aus: ihr Ziel, recht rein und hoch gedacht, ist gar nicht der freie Gebildete, sondern der Gelehrte, der wissenschaftliche Mensch und zwar der möglichst früh nutzbare wissenschaftliche Mensch, der sich abseits von dem Leben stellt, um es recht deutlich zu erkennen; ihr Resultat, recht empirisch-gemein angeschaut, ist der historisch-aesthetische Bildungsphilister, der altkluge und neuweise Schwätzer über Staat, Kirche und Kunst, das Sensorium für tausenderlei Anempfindungen, der unersättliche Magen, der doch nicht weiss, was ein rechtschaffner Hunger und Durst ist. Dass eine Erziehung mit jenem Ziele und mit diesem Resultate eine widernatürliche ist, das fühlt nur der in ihr noch nicht fertig gewordene Mensch, das fühlt allein der Instinct der Jugend, weil sie noch den Instinct der Natur hat, der erst künstlich und gewaltsam durch jene Erziehung gebrochen wird. Wer aber diese Erziehung wiederum brechen will, der muss der Jugend zum Worte verhelfen, der muss ihrem unbewussten Widerstreben mit der Helligkeit der Begriffe voranleuchten und es zu einem bewussten und laut redenden Bewusstsein machen (Nietzsche, 1980d, p. 325-326).

²⁷ Formt in euch ein Bild, dem die Zukunft entsprechen soll (Nietzsche, 1980d, p. 295).

²⁸ Eigenschaft dieses modernen Menschen: der merkwürdige Gegensatz eines Innern, dem kein Aeusseres, eines Aeusseren, dem kein Inneres entspricht (Nietzsche, 1980d, p. 272).

²⁹ Unsere moderne Bildung ist eben deshalb nichts Lebendiges, weil sie ohne jenen Gegensatz sich gar nicht begreifen lässt, das heisst: sie ist gar keine wirkliche Bildung, sondern nur eine Art Wissen um die Bildung (Nietzsche, 1980d, p. 273).

³⁰ The entire passage reads: Von diesen Hoffenden weiss ich, dass sie alle diese Allgemeinheiten aus der Nähe verstehn und mit ihrer eigensten Erfahrung in eine persönlich gemeinte Lehre sich übersetzen werden; die Andern mögen einstweilen nichts als verdeckte Schüsseln wahrnehmen, die wohl auch leer sein können; bis sie einmal überrascht mit eignen Augen sehen, dass die Schüsseln gefüllt sind und dass Angriffe, Forderungen, Lebenstriebe, Leidenschaften in diesen Allgemeinheiten eingeschachtelt und zusammengedrückt lagen, die nicht lange Zeit so verdeckt liegen konnten. Diese Zweifler auf die Zeit, die alles an's Licht bringt, verweisend, wende ich mich zum Schluss an jene Gesellschaft der Hoffenden, um ihnen den Gang und Verlauf ihrer Heilung, ihrer Errettung von der historischen Krankheit und damit ihre eigne Geschichte bis zu

dem Zeitpunkt durch ein Gleichniss zu erzählen, wo sie wieder gesund genug sein werden, von Neuem Historie zu treiben und sich der Vergangenheit unter der Herrschaft des Lebens, in jenem dreifachen Sinne, nämlich monumental oder antiquarisch oder kritisch, zu bedienen. In jenem Zeitpunkt werden sie unwissender sein, als die "Gebildeten" der Gegenwart; denn sie werden viel verlernt und sogar alle Lust verloren haben, nach dem, was jene Gebildeten vor allem wissen wollen, überhaupt noch hinzublicken; ihre Kennzeichen sind, von dem Gesichtsfelde jener Gebildeten aus gesehen, gerade ihre "Unbildung," ihre Gleichgültigkeit und Verschlossenheit gegen vieles Berühmte, selbst gegen manches Gute. Aber sie sind, an jenem Endpunkte ihrer Heilung, wieder Menschen geworden und haben aufgehört, menschenähnliche Aggregate zu sein—das ist etwas! Das sind noch Hoffnungen! (Nietzsche, 1980d, p. 332).